

Adapting the EC Model to the Frequency Dependency of Binaural Masking Level Differences – Is this Relevant for Speech in Noise?

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Abstract – Several binaural speech intelligibility models simulate human binaural processing using the Equalization-Cancellation (EC) mechanism, incorporating processing inaccuracies based on tone-in-noise detection at 500 Hz. Despite this, such inaccuracies are typically assumed to be frequency-independent in binaural speech intelligibility models. This study examines the validity of that assumption and explores how auditory filter bandwidth affects binaural masking release. Experiment I measured tone detection thresholds across frequencies from 250 to 2000 Hz in 12 normal-hearing and 5 hearing-impaired listeners, varying the interaural phase difference (IPD) of noise between 0 and 5π . Results were compared with EC model predictions. Binaural inaccuracies showed a low-pass effect, reducing binaural masking level differences (BMLDs) at higher frequencies. However, the EC model inaccurately predicted BMLDs at 250 Hz. Experiment II involved a subset of listeners performing speech-in-noise intelligibility tasks with low-pass filtered speech. This allowed assessment of whether tone-in-noise detection could predict speech recognition thresholds (SRTs), particularly in hearing-impaired individuals whose low-frequency hearing remained near normal. Findings revealed that adapting the model’s binaural inaccuracies improved SRT predictions beyond audiometric thresholds alone.

Keywords. Binaural, Tone-in-Noise, Binaural Processing Inaccuracies, Speech in Noise, Hearing Impairment

1. Introduction

Several binaural speech intelligibility models have successfully been used to predict the outcome of speech intelligibility experiments in different acoustic scenarios ranging from anechoic conditions to reverberant conditions [e.g. 1–8]. These models can be separated into a front-end, which mimics human auditory processing, and a back-end, which quantifies the usable speech information in the acoustical signal. The front-end usually consists of a band-

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27 pass filterbank [e.g. a gammatone filterbank; 9] to mimic the frequency selectivity of the auditory system and an
 28 equalization-cancellation (EC) mechanism [10] to model the effective binaural auditory processing of human listen-
 29 ers. The back-end usually consists of an intrusive model like the Speech Intelligibility Index [SII; 11], the Speech
 30 Transmission Index [STI; 12], the short-time Objective Intelligibility [STOI; 13] measure or a non-intrusive model [for
 31 an overview see e.g. 14].

32 The EC model [10] uses interaural differences in the target signal and the interfering signal to improve the signal-to-
 33 noise ratio (SNR) especially at low frequencies. In the EC model, first, the left ear and right ear channels are equalized
 34 in level, such that the interaural level difference (ILD) is compensated. This processing approximates the compressive
 35 behavior of the cochlear. In a second step, the interaural time difference (ITD) or the interaural phase difference (IPD)
 36 between the left and right ear is equalized such that the SNR at the output of the EC stage, which is calculated by
 37 subtracting left and right ear channel from each other, is improved. The EC processing can be used to describe the
 38 outcome of narrow-band experiments like tone-in-noise detection tasks, but also for broad-band signals like speech,
 39 where independent EC processing across frequency bands is assumed. In this way, the EC stage can account for the
 40 binaural release from masking, which is observed when a target source and an interfering source differ in their ITDs or
 41 IPDs, or – more ecologically relevant – if they differ in their spatial location. The EC model, however, overestimates the
 42 binaural release from masking especially in anechoic conditions [2, 10, 15, 16]. To compensate for this overestimation,
 43 binaural processing inaccuracies have been incorporated into the EC model in order to limit the resolution of the
 44 equalization process in level and time. Consequently, no perfect cancellation can be achieved if the binaural processing
 45 inaccuracies are used and the SNR improvement is limited. The binaural processing inaccuracies have first been derived
 46 by Durlach [10], where the ITD inaccuracy was assumed to be a normally-distributed random variable with zero mean
 47 and a standard deviation of 105 μs . This has been modified by vom Hövel [16], who fitted the binaural processing
 48 inaccuracies to binaural tone-in-noise detection thresholds obtained in an experiment by Langford and Jeffress [17]
 49 for jittering the ITD and to binaural tone-in-noise detection thresholds obtained in an experiment by Egan [18] for
 50 jittering the ILD. Both measurements were obtained for a single frequency of 500 Hz with normal-hearing listeners.
 51 In the experiment by Langford and Jeffress [17] tone detection thresholds were obtained in broadband noise, where
 52 the ITD of the noise was varied. In the experiment by Egan [18], the tone detection thresholds were obtained, while
 53 the ILD of the noise was varied. The processing inaccuracies derived by vom Hövel [16] are assumed to be normally
 54 distributed random variables with zero mean, and – in contrast to Durlach [10] - a standard deviation which is a
 55 function of ITD and ILD, respectively. These standard deviations of the processing inaccuracies are given by

$$\sigma_{\delta} = \sigma_{\delta 0} \cdot \left[1 + \frac{|\Delta|}{\Delta_0}\right], \quad (1)$$

56 and

$$\sigma_{\epsilon} = \sigma_{\epsilon 0} \cdot \left[1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha_0}\right)^p\right], \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Standard deviations of the ITD error σ_δ and ILD error σ_ϵ in the EC mechanism derived by vom Hövel [16]. The standard deviation of the ITD error is assumed to grow linearly with increasing ITD, while the ILD error in dB grows exponentially with increasing ILD (in dB).

57 with $\sigma_{\delta 0} = 65\mu\text{s}$, $\Delta_0 = 1.6\text{ms}$, $\sigma_{\epsilon 0} = 1.5\text{dB}$, $\alpha_0 = 15\text{dB}$, and $p=1.6$ [16].

58 These values have for example been used in the binaural speech intelligibility models by Beutelmann et al. [2] and
 59 Andersen et al. [5], Hauth and Brand [7], and Hauth et al. [8]. Figure 1 shows the standard deviations of the ITD
 60 and ILD inaccuracies as derived by vom Hövel [16]. The standard deviation of the ITD processing inaccuracy is
 61 defined in the time domain and assumed to grow linearly with ITD. The standard deviation for an ITD of 0 μs (and
 62 thus the intercept) was set to 65 μs . The standard deviation of the ILD processing inaccuracy is assumed to grow
 63 exponentially with increasing absolute value of the ILD. In the binaural speech intelligibility models mentioned above,
 64 these processing inaccuracies are applied in each frequency band, and therefore, are assumed to be independent of
 65 center frequency. However, it is unclear if this assumption is valid, because, to our knowledge, a frequency dependency
 66 of the binaural processing inaccuracies has not yet been investigated and compared to predictions of binaural speech
 67 intelligibility models using the EC model.

68 Binaural unmasking, which relies on ITDs or IPDs, gets worse with increasing frequency[e.g. 19]. The same holds
 69 for the ability of the auditory system to preserve the temporal fine structure of a stimulus, which gets also worse
 70 with increasing frequency and is often called “phase locking”. The loss of phase locking has been regarded as the main
 71 reason for the reduction of BMLDs with increasing frequency [20, 21]. The time domain implementation of the binaural
 72 processing inaccuracy in the EC mechanism generally accounts for this finding for the N_0S_π or $N_\pi S_0$ condition (where
 73 either the phase of the speech or the noise is interaurally inverted, while the phase of the respective other is not). The
 74 constant ITD inaccuracy leads to an increasing IPD inaccuracy with increasing frequency resulting in a decreasing
 75 BMLD with increasing frequency. However, this implementation implies that the predicted BMLD at 250 Hz is even
 76 higher than at 500 Hz, which has not been observed in binaural tone detection experiments so far. For example,
 77 van de Par and Kohlrausch [19] investigated the effect of masker bandwidth and center frequency on binaural release
 78 from masking. Their data indicate that the binaural release from masking gets smaller for frequencies below 500 Hz
 79 in the $N_\pi S_0$ condition (see their Figure 1). Taken together, it is still not clear, whether predicting BMLDs in tone-
 80 in-noise detection experiments at different center frequencies might require frequency dependent binaural processing
 81 inaccuracies in the EC model.

82 Moreover, this study analyzed if the binaural processing inaccuracy can be described as a function of ITD and how
 83 predictions with the EC model incorporating these binaural processing inaccuracies change for large ITDs. Physiological

84 measurements in mammals suggest that the binaural neurons respond best to an ITD which is within a half-cycle (π)
85 of the corresponding frequency band [22]. That’s why nearly all binaural models restrict the binaural processing stages
86 to use temporal binaural cues within the so called “ π -limit”. Both questions were addressed in Experiment I, where
87 the frequency dependency of BMLD curves was investigated in 12 listeners with normal hearing and 5 listeners with
88 high-frequency hearing loss. The results obtained in the listening experiments were compared to BMLD predictions of
89 the EC model.

90 In Experiment II, binaural speech intelligibility experiments were performed by a subset of the same listeners in order
91 to test the hypothesis, if tone-detection performance is reflected in binaural speech reception thresholds (SRTs), i.e., if
92 better tone detection is related to better SRTs. We expected, that this experiment might reveal differences in binaural
93 unmasking between listeners with normal and with impaired hearing, which could potentially be used to improve SRT
94 predictions for listeners with impaired hearing. In this study, the binaural speech intelligibility model by Beutelmann
95 et al. [2] was used, which considers the individual pure-tone audiogram using a threshold simulating noise. However,
96 it has been shown that the effect of hearing impairment was not fully accounted for by incorporating the audiogram
97 alone as it does not reflect, for instance, supra-threshold deficits [23, 24] and potential individual binaural processing
98 capabilities. In a study conducted by Neher et al. [25] it was shown that listeners with hearing impairment differed
99 in their binaural intelligibility difference (BILD), which is the binaural release from masking by spatially separating
100 the target speech source from the interfering noise source in a speech intelligibility experiment, and BMLDs at 500 Hz
101 even though they were matched in age, hearing loss (according to the pure-tone audiogram), and cognitive factors.
102 This finding suggested that supra-threshold deficits are reflected in binaural tone detection thresholds and should,
103 therefore, also be accounted for in binaural speech intelligibility models.

104 The SRTs of Experiment II were predicted using BSIM with individual adapted binaural processing inaccuracies,
105 which were derived based on the binaural tone detection thresholds from Experiment I. It was hypothesized that these
106 individually adjusted binaural processing inaccuracies lead to better predictions of the individual SRTs. Both listeners
107 with normal hearing and with hearing impairment performed SRT measurements for low-pass filtered speech with a
108 cut-off frequency of 1500 Hz, in order to exclude effects of high frequency hearing loss and to focus on the frequency
109 region, where binaural unmasking can be assumed to be largest.

110 2. Methods

111 *Listeners*

112 12 listeners with normal hearing and 5 listeners with impaired hearing participated in Experiment I. 8 of the
113 12 normally hearing listeners and the hearing-impaired listeners of Experiment I also participated in Experiment II.
114 Normal hearing was guaranteed by standard pure-tone audiometry at the frequencies 125, 250, 500, 1000, 2000, 3000,
115 4000, 6000, and 8000 Hz, where none of the thresholds exceeded 20 dB HL. Hearing impaired listeners with nearly
116 normal hearing at frequencies up to 1000 Hz were chosen in order to reduce low-frequency audibility effects on the

Figure 2. Audiograms of the listeners with hearing impairment. The left and right panels show the audiogram of the left and right ear, respectively.

117 BMLD measurements. Figure 2 shows the individual audiograms of the listeners with impaired hearing. Up to 1000 Hz,
 118 these listeners had audiometric thresholds, which were better than 30 dB HL.

119 *Experiment I: Binaural Tone-in-Noise Detection*

120 The first experiment was a binaural tone-in-noise detection task, similar to the BMLD measurements by Langford
 121 and Jeffress [17]. Binaural tone-in-noise detection thresholds were determined for carrier frequencies of 250, 500, 750,
 122 1000, 1500, and 2000 Hz for listeners with normal hearing and for 500, 750, 1000, and 1500 Hz for the listeners with
 123 impaired hearing. Tone detection was investigated in Gaussian white noise, which was bandpass filtered between 100-
 124 4000 Hz. The broad-band noise was preferred over narrow band noise because it allows for an easier discrimination
 125 between target tone and interfering noise. Moreover, the experiments by Langford and Jeffress [17] and Egan [18] were
 126 also performed using broadband noise. A 3-alternative-forced-choice (AFC) 1-up-2-down procedure converging to the
 127 70.7% correct point on the psychometric function was used to determine tone detection thresholds.

128 *Apparatus*

129 The stimuli were generated using MATLAB (MathWorks, Natick, MA, USA) using the AFC Toolbox (Version 1.4),
 130 developed by Stephan Ewert at Carl von Ossietzky Universität, Oldenburg, Germany, and presented binaurally via an
 131 RME Fireface UC soundcard (Audio AG, Haimhausen, Germany) and HD 650 headphones (Sennheiser, Wedemark,
 132 Germany). The sound output was calibrated to dB SPL using a Brüel&Kjaer (B&K, Nærum, Denmark) 4153 artificial
 133 ear, a B&K 4134 half-inch microphone, a B&K 2669 preamplifier, and a B&K 2610 measuring amplifier. The noise
 134 level was set to 75 dB SPL and the level of the tone was varied to find the individual threshold. The experiments were
 135 conducted in a double-walled, sound-attenuated booth.

136 *Stimuli*

137 The target tone was always presented diotically (S_0), i.e., the same signal was presented to both ears. According
 138 to Langford and Jeffress [17], the tested ITDs of the noise were selected to mirror fixed IPDs for each tested frequency
 139 ranging from 0 to 5π in steps of $\pi/2$ leading to frequency dependent ITDs. For example, ITDs ranging from 0 to 5 ms
 140 in steps of 0.5 ms were used at 500 Hz, while the ITDs ranging from 0 ms to 10 ms in steps of 1 ms were used at
 141 250 Hz. This method was chosen, because binaural release from masking is largest using IPD of π in either the tone
 142 or the noise.

143 *Experiment II: Binaural Speech-in-Noise Experiments*

144 In Experiment II, a binaural speech-in-noise test was conducted with the same listeners as in Experiment I. Speech
 145 intelligibility experiments were conducted using the Oldenburg Sentence Test [OlSa, 26–28] in speech-shaped stationary
 146 noise with the same long term average spectrum of the speech. In the remainder of this article, this noise is referred
 147 to as “Olnoise”. OlSa sentences consist of five-word-sentences with a fixed grammatical structure noun-verb-numeral-
 148 adjective-object, where each word is randomly selected from a list of 10 words. To determine the SRT for 50% correctly
 149 understood words, an adaptive procedure was used for controlling the level of the speech [Equation 9, 29] and the
 150 SRT was estimated using a maximum likelihood fit. Each SRT was determined using a list of 20 sentences, which was
 151 randomly selected out of 45 lists. Because the main focus of this study lied on the binaural processing capabilities of
 152 the listeners, speech and noise stimuli were modified as follows: Both speech and noise signals were low-pass filtered
 153 with a cut off frequency of 1500 Hz in order to minimize the influence of the high frequency hearing loss for the listeners
 154 with hearing impairment while keeping their ability for binaurally processing the signals, which is most effective at low
 155 frequencies. To be able to compare the results obtained for normal-hearing listeners and hearing-impaired listeners,
 156 the listeners with normal hearing were provided with the same stimuli as the hearing-impaired listeners. In total, 4
 157 SRTs were obtained for each listener: 1) monaural SRT for the left ear, 2) monaural SRTs for the right ear, 3) diotic
 158 SRTs, i.e., the same signals are presented to the left and right ear (N_0S_0), and 4) dichotic SRTs, where the phase
 159 of the noise was inverted between both ears ($N_\pi S_0$). This was done in order to be able to compare the outcome of
 160 the speech intelligibility tests with the binaural tone-in-noise detection experiment in a frequency region, where the
 161 listeners with hearing impairment showed nearly normal hearing thresholds according to the audiogram.

162 *Model predictions*

163 The binaural speech intelligibility model [BSIM, 2] consist of two stages: the front-end, that predicts the improve-
 164 ment of the SNR due to binaural unmasking and better ear listening, and the back-end that predicts the speech
 165 intelligibility. In the front-end, the EC model is applied in order to predict the improvement of the SNR due to binau-
 166 ral processing. To achieve this, the input signal is filtered into 30 ERB-spaced [30] frequency bands using a gammatone
 167 filter bank [9]. The listener’s individual hearing threshold is considered by adding a Threshold Simulating Noise (TSN)
 168 to each ear. This TSN is calculated by adding the frequency specific dB HL values to the threshold of normal hearing

169 listener in dB SPL as defined in EN-ISO389-7 [31], where the threshold is determined binaurally in the free-field and
 170 is referred to as Minimum Audible Field (MAF). The TSN is uncorrelated between the ears, so that the EC model
 171 cannot cancel it. Afterwards, EC processing is applied in each frequency channel to improve the SNR. Finally, the
 172 resulting SNR is compared to the monaural SNRs at the left and right ear channel and the maximum of all three
 173 alternatives is considered as the result of the first stage.

174 The model’s back-end uses the output of the front-end and estimates the speech intelligibility using the Speech
 175 Intelligibility Index [SII, 11]. The SII is calculated essentially as a weighted sum of the band-specific SNRs. Before the
 176 summation, the band-specific SNRs are limited to a range from -15 dB and 15 dB. The weighting is given by a band
 177 importance function, which mimics the importance of the individual frequency bands for human speech recognition,
 178 resulting in an SII value between 0 and 1. In this study, the NNS (various nonsense syllable tests where most of the
 179 English phonemes occur equally often) weighting function [11] was used. The resulting SII values can then be mapped
 180 to intelligibility values. In this study, only SRT values are analyzed. Therefore, only the reference SII at the SRT is
 181 required, which we set to an SII value of 0.2. This value matches the SRT of -7.1 dB of listeners with normal-hearing
 182 for OISa sentences in broadband speech shaped noise [28]. The front-end of the model without using the back-end was
 183 applied to the signals of Experiment I in order to evaluate how closely the tone-in-noise threshold of the model can be
 184 predicted by BSIMs front-end. This was done in two ways: Firstly, using the frequency independent processing errors
 185 derived for 500 Hz by vom Hövel [16] in the EC processing, in order to test the hypothesis of frequency independent
 186 binaural processing inaccuracies. And secondly, using optimized frequency dependent binaural processing accuracies,
 187 in order to test the hypothesis, that this can improve the prediction accuracy.

188 The complete BSIM consisting of front-end and back-end is then applied to the results of Experiment II. Again,
 189 this was done using the original frequency independent binaural processing inaccuracies and the frequency dependent
 190 processing accuracies derived based on the results of Experiment I. The underlying hypothesis of this approach is that
 191 the same enhancement mechanism is used by the human auditory system for narrow-band tone-in-noise tasks and for
 192 broad-band speech-in-noise tasks.

193 3. Results

194 *Experiment I: Binaural Tone-in-Noise Measurements*

195 Figure 3 shows the BMLDs obtained in the binaural tone-in-noise detection task for the 12 listeners with normal
 196 hearing and the BMLDs predicted by the EC model. The BMLD denotes the relative improvement of the tone detection
 197 threshold in the dichotic condition relative to the diotic condition. The BMLD is high if the ITD of the noise results
 198 in a phase shift corresponding to odd (1, 3, 5) multiples of π at the tested frequency, and low if the ITD corresponds
 199 to phase shifts of even (2, 4) multiples of π . This results in a periodic pattern of the BMLD, which can be observed in
 200 Figure 3 and is referred to as “Jeffress curves”. The largest BMLD of approximately 11 dB can be observed at 500 Hz
 201 for an ITD of the noise of 1 ms, corresponding to a phase shift of π , which is in line with results from the literature [e.g.
 202 17]. With increasing frequency, the maximum achievable BMLD is reduced by approximately 4 dB at 1000 Hz and by

Figure 3. Binaural Masking Level Differences (BMLD) measured in 12 listeners with normal hearing (gray diamonds). The tested frequencies of the tone were 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1500, and 2000 Hz. The IPD of the noise was varied from 0 to 5π in steps of 0.5π , leading to a frequency dependent ITD. For example, an IPD of π corresponds to an ITD of the noise of 1ms at 500 Hz and to 0.5 ms at 1000 Hz. Additionally, the IPD of $\frac{3\pi}{4}$ corresponding to an ITD of 0.75 ms at 500 Hz was measured for all frequencies, which corresponds approximately to the maximum anatomically achievable ITD considering human head size. Two model versions were used: one with 1 ERB wide auditory filters and one with 2.3 ERB wide auditory filters.

203 6 dB at 2000 Hz. This finding is in line with literature [e.g. 19], where a correlation between the binaural release from
 204 masking and the capability of phase locking on the auditory nerve was observed. Interestingly, the BMLD observed
 205 for an IPD of $\frac{3\pi}{4}$, which corresponds to an ITD of 750 μ s at 500 Hz, is always as good as for an IPD of π for all tested
 206 frequencies. For the tested frequency of 250 Hz (top-left panel of Figure 3), the BMLD is reduced compared to the
 207 500 Hz condition: For an IPD of the noise of π , the BMLD at 250 Hz is 8 dB, which is 3 dB lower than the BMLD
 208 obtained at 500 Hz. The reason for this is two-fold: Firstly, the diotic threshold is lower at 250 Hz than at 500 Hz,
 209 because the auditory filter can be assumed to be narrower at 250 Hz than at 500 Hz. According to the definition of
 210 the equivalent rectangular bandwidth ($ERB = 24.7 \cdot (4.37 \cdot f[kHz] + 1)$ [30]), the reduction of masking by using the
 211 filter at 250 Hz and the same broad band noise can be up to 1.8 dB. This can also be found in the data, where the
 212 median diotic threshold at 250 Hz is reduced by 1.25 dB compared to the diotic threshold at 500 Hz, which is slightly
 213 lower than the theoretical value according to the ERB formula described above (see Figure 4).
 214 Secondly, the dichotic thresholds are statistically significantly increased by approximately 2 dB in the 250 Hz condition
 215 compared to the 500 Hz condition (t-test, $p=0.021$). In addition to the effect of center frequency on BMLD, also an
 216 effect of the tested IPD can be observed: With increasing IPD of the noise, the maximum achievable BMLD decreases
 217 from π to 3π and from 3π to 5π almost independently of center frequency. Figure 5 shows the differences between

Figure 4. Diotic ($N_0 S_0$) and dichotic ($N_\pi S_0$) tone detection thresholds obtained at 250 Hz (open circles) and 500 Hz (open diamonds).

Figure 5. Difference between BMLDs (ΔBMLD) for an IPD of π and an IPD of 3π (left panel) and for an IPD of 3π and an IPD of 5π (right panel). A negative ΔBMLD indicates that the tone detection threshold obtained at an IPD of π is lower (better) than at the tone detection threshold obtained at an IPD of 3π .

218 BMLDs (ΔBMLD) between π and 3π (left panel) and between 3π and 5π (right panel). Note, that the ΔBMLD s are
 219 identical to the differences between the dichotic tone detection thresholds, as the diotic thresholds are compensated
 220 due to the difference calculation. The largest difference in dichotic tone detection thresholds can be observed at 250 Hz,
 221 where the median difference is -4.8 dB. At 500 Hz, a difference of -4 dB is observed, which is reduced to -2.5 dB at
 222 750 Hz, to -2 dB at 1500 Hz, and to 0.8 dB at 2000 Hz. A Bonferroni corrected pair-wise comparison revealed a
 223 statistical difference in the BMLD differences between 250 Hz and 750 Hz as well as between 250 Hz and 2000 Hz.
 224 Moreover, the difference observed at 500 Hz was statistically significant different from the difference observed at
 225 2000 Hz. No statistical difference was observed in the tone detection threshold differences between an IPD of 3π and
 226 5π at the tested frequencies. The differences are in the range from -2.8 to -3 dB independent of frequency, except for
 227 250 Hz and 150 Hz, where the difference is below -2 dB.

228 3.1. *EC-model predictions: effects of phase shift and frequency*

229 The EC stage with processing inaccuracies derived by vom Hövel [16] is able to predict the decreasing BMLD with
 230 increasing frequency (connected black dots of Figure 3). This is a consequence of the model’s processing inaccuracy,
 231 which is defined in the time domain and thus, its effect increases with increasing frequency, where an IPD of π
 232 corresponds to an ITD which is decreased by a factor of 2 per frequency increase of one octave. However, for 250 Hz,
 233 the predicted BMLD for the delay corresponding to a phase shift of π is with about 16 dB much larger than the
 234 measured BMLD with about 9 dB. Similar differences were also found for an ITD of 6 ms (3π). While the measured
 235 BMLDs for 250 Hz tend to be smaller compared to the 500 Hz condition, the predicted BMLD is larger.

236 Moreover, it can be seen, that even though the BMLD is generally well predicted for the first cycle (from $0:2\pi$), the
 237 prediction gets worse for larger ITDs of the noise. The BMLDs are overpredicted even though the binaural processing
 238 inaccuracy of the model increases with increasing ITD.

239 The effect of reduced BMLDs for an IPD of 3π or 5π relative to π is conserved because a side maximum (and not
 240 the main peak) of the cross-correlation function is used for estimating the ITD. Therefore, the cancellation is not as
 241 effective as it is for an IPD of π . The linearly growing errors introduced by vom Hövel [16] basically mirror the effect
 242 of the π -limit. Both are incorporated in the BSIM model and do not affect the relative differences of the predicted
 243 BMLD for odd multiples of π .

244 3.2. *EC-model predictions: use of wider auditory filters*

245 As mentioned above, the π -limit depends on the width of the auditory filters. We evaluated if BMLD predictions
 246 change when the EC model is used with effectively wider binaural auditory filters. This is motivated by Beutelmann
 247 et al. [32] who showed that wider (binaural) peripheral filters better explain SRTs in noise, when the IPD of the noise
 248 differed in adjacent frequency bands. This does not mean that the human auditory filters per se are wider just because
 249 binaural processing is involved. These “wider” binaural filters might just indicate that across frequency processing
 250 (using two different auditory filters across ears) takes place in binaural processing, which can be modeled in a simplified
 251 way by increasing the bandwidths of the monaural auditory filters. Beutelmann et al. [32] found that increasing the
 252 bandwidth of the auditory filters by a factor of 2.3 led to the maximum congruency between predicted and observed
 253 SRTs.

254 In order to test the hypothesis that across frequency processing affects the BMLD in tone in noise experiments
 255 especially for ITDs, which are larger than the frequency specific π -limit, we used the same binaural bandwidth (2.3
 256 ERB) for the EC model. As hypothesized, this approach improved the prediction accuracy for ITDs, which are larger
 257 than the corresponding periods of the gammatone filters, especially for frequencies below 1000 Hz. The results are
 258 shown by the black triangles in Figure 3. The predictions of the first BMLD cycle (from 0 to 2π) are not affected by
 259 the wider binaural filters.

Figure 6. Individual BMLDs for the hearing-impaired listeners in comparison with the normal hearing data and model data.

Figure 7. SRTs of the normal-hearing listeners (box plots) and hearing-impaired listeners (individual datapoints). The listening conditions are: monaurally left ear (“MonL”), monaurally right ear (“MonR”), diotic, and dichotic with interaurally phase-inverted noise. Model predictions (black bullets) are only shown for the diotic and dichotic condition. The BSIM prediction with ITD processing inaccuracy matched to the average of listeners HI2, HI3, HI4, and HI5 is shown as diamond. HI1 can be considered as binaurally normally hearing.

260 3.3. Listeners with hearing loss

261 A subset of the tone in noise experiments for the frequencies 500, 750, 1000, and 1500 Hz was also performed
 262 by 5 listeners with high frequency hearing loss. Figure 6 shows the individual BMLDs for the listeners with hearing
 263 impairment. The results show a large variability across listeners. HI1 (black squares) performs best at 500 Hz (even
 264 better than most of the normal hearing listeners and as good as the EC model), while HI1 performs worst at 1500 Hz.
 265 This indicates that binaural unmasking in these hearing-impaired listeners can be reduced on a very individual level
 266 even though the hearing loss in these listeners at the test frequencies would be typically regarded as close to neglectable.
 267 In the following we evaluate, if reduced BMLDs in tone-in-noise experiments is related to a reduced binaural unmasking
 268 in speech-in-noise experiments and how this can be included in the model.

Table 1. BMLD measured at 500 Hz and corresponding binaural processing inaccuracy (given as σ_{δ_0} in Equation 1) in the EC mechanism. The reference value of σ_{δ_0} for normally hearing listeners according to vom Hövel [16] is 65 μ s

Listener	Measured BMLD [dB]	Processing Inaccuracy [μ s]
HI1	13.9	45
HI2	8.7	95
HI3	7.7	110
HI4	9.2	90
HI5	9.2	90

269 3.4. Experiment II: Binaural Speech in Noise Experiments

270 Figure 7 shows the SRTs, where both speech and noise were low-pass filtered with a cut-off frequency of 1500 Hz.
 271 Boxplots indicate the SRTs of 8 normally hearing listeners, the individual SRTs of the listeners with impaired hearing
 272 are shown as squares in the same way as in Experiment I. SRTs were obtained for the left and right ear, separately.
 273 Additionally, the diotic SRTs and the dichotic SRTs, where the phase of the noise was interaurally inverted, were
 274 measured.

275 In the monaural conditions and in the diotic condition, the median SRTs for the normal-hearing listeners are observed
 276 at -3 to -4 dB. In the dichotic condition, SRTs are reduced by 7 dB, such that a median SRT of -11 dB is obtained. One
 277 listener even achieved an SRT of -17 dB. Based on the individual results observed in the tone-in-noise detection task,
 278 the individual binaural processing inaccuracy was derived for each listener with hearing impairment. The individual
 279 BMLD obtained at 500 Hz and a time delay of the noise corresponding to an interaural phase shift of π was chosen as
 280 a reference for fitting the binaural processing inaccuracy of the EC mechanism. This binaural processing inaccuracy
 281 was derived by changing it adaptively until the difference between measured BMLD and predicted BMLD was smaller
 282 than 0.25 dB. The individual values for each hearing-impaired listener are shown in Table 1. Note, that BSIM already
 283 considers the listener’s individual hearing loss using a threshold-simulating noise. In these simulations we evaluate, if
 284 the additional consideration of a reduced binaural processing accuracy can improve BSIMs prediction accuracy. Note
 285 that assessment of the individual binaural processing inaccuracies from Experiment I was rather rough and that the
 286 resulting differences in predicted SRTs between HI2, HI3, HI4, and HI5 were rather small. Consequently, we present
 287 the model prediction for only one average value of the standard deviation of the processing inaccuracy of 100 μ s. For
 288 listener HI3, the assumed standard deviation of 65 μ s for normally hearing listeners was used, as HI1 can be considered
 289 as normally hearing listener in both, the tone-in-noise and the speech-in-noise experiment. The other listeners with
 290 impaired hearing, however, show worse performance in both, the tone-in-noise and in the speech-in-noise experiment.
 291 Furthermore, these hearing-impaired listeners show worse monaural and diotic SRTs as well.

292 BSIM slightly overestimates the SRT in the diotic condition, but matches the median SRT in the dichotic condition.
 293 By increasing the model’s internal standard deviation of ITD inaccuracy from 65 μ s to 100 μ s, the predicted dichotic
 294 SRT is increased by approximately 3 dB and shows better agreement with the listeners with hearing impairment
 295 except for HI1, who performs like the listeners with normal hearing.

296 **4. General Discussion**297 *Frequency dependency of binaural processing inaccuracy*

298 Binaural tone-in-noise detection experiments were performed to investigate the frequency dependency of BMLDs.
 299 The BMLDs obtained with 12 listeners with normal hearing were compared to predictions using an EC model, where
 300 binaural processing inaccuracies were considered. So far, these inaccuracies were solely determined for 500 Hz and
 301 assumed to jitter temporal information rather than phase information. It has been shown that the inaccuracy inves-
 302 tigated for 500 Hz, which has originally been applied by vom Hövel (1984) to the EC model, can be used to predict
 303 BMLDs also for higher frequencies. Because the binaural processing inaccuracy is defined to have a constant standard
 304 deviation in microseconds, the detrimental effect becomes more prominent with increasing frequency as the cancella-
 305 tion requires an equalized phase.

306 The finding, that the binaural unmasking becomes less effective with increasing frequency can be explained by the fact
 307 that an accurate coding of the temporal fine structure is required by the binaural system to achieve a high BMLD.
 308 The loss of phase locking with increasing frequency is assumed to limit the performance in the dichotic conditions of
 309 binaural tone-in-noise experiments (e.g. Bernstein and Trahiotis, 1996). The same trend is captured by the EC model,
 310 even though phase locking is not explicitly accounted for in the model. However, the processing inaccuracies are im-
 311 plemented in the time domain. With increasing frequency, the effect of the inaccuracy gets larger as the same phase
 312 relation between both ears is achieved at a much smaller delay. Therefore, the impact of the delay inaccuracy gets
 313 larger with increasing frequency, leading to a less accurate equalization in time and, consequently, to a less effective
 314 cancellation of the interfering source or noise. At 250 Hz, a larger deviation between the perceptual data and the
 315 predicted BMLD was observed. In the dichotic condition, the thresholds for 250 Hz are only slightly worse than in the
 316 500 Hz condition. However, the EC mechanism predicts the thresholds to be even better than at 500 Hz. Therefore,
 317 the standard deviation of the processing inaccuracy needs to be increased to 130 μs at 250 Hz, while it can remain
 318 to be 65 μs at frequencies of 500 Hz and above. The periodic pattern with increasing ITD, which can be observed at
 319 500 Hz and higher frequencies, is less prominent at 250 Hz. This might be caused by the relatively large ITDs of more
 320 than 5 ms, which are much larger than any ITD the auditory system usually has to deal with and therefore might be
 321 too large to be used by the human binaural system.

322 *Increased filter bandwidth of the EC model*

323 The same data was modeled using the EC model according to Beutelmann et al. [32] with 2.3 ERB wide filters
 324 instead of 1 ERB wide filters like in Beutelmann et al. [2]. The 2.3 ERB wide filters better described the perceptual
 325 data than the 1 ERB wide filters. This indicates that the 2.3 ERB wide filters not only explain the binaural unmasking
 326 of broadband speech signals better [as concluded in 32] but also of the narrow band signal used here. However, changing
 327 the effective binaural bandwidth only influences BMLDs for ITDs which correspond to IPDs larger than 2π . This can
 328 be explained by the fact that by increasing the bandwidth of the auditory filters, the correlation of the secondary
 329 maxima between left and right ear is reduced leading to a reduction of predicted BMLDs.

330 *Individualization of processing inaccuracies for listeners with impaired hearing*

331 The listeners with impaired hearing showed a large variance of BMLDs. Four of five listeners had a reduced
332 BMLD, and one listener showed BMLDs at 500 Hz, which were as good as the BMLDs for listeners with normal
333 hearing. However, these findings were not consistent across frequencies.

334 In the binaural speech intelligibility experiment, those listeners with impaired hearing, who showed a reduced BMLD
335 in the tone detection task at 500 Hz, also showed reduced dichotic SRTs. The hearing-impaired listener with normal
336 BMLDs showed a normal dichotic SRT. Similar observations were made in a study by Neher et al. [25], where a negative
337 association between BILD and SRTs was observed (higher BILDs were associated to lower SRTs). Interestingly, in
338 their experiment it was also shown, that listeners with higher BILDs benefited more from low-frequency binaural
339 cues in spatial speech intelligibility experiments than from low frequency SNR improvement provided by the tested
340 algorithm, while listeners with low BILDs showed more benefit from low-frequency SNR improvement than from a
341 preservation of binaural cues.

342 In order to evaluate whether the predictions of BSIM can be improved by taking these differences between listeners
343 better into account, the processing inaccuracy in the EC stage of BSIM was adapted in order to fit the BMLD at
344 500 Hz : Four listeners with impaired hearing were considered with virtually the same ITD inaccuracy of 100 μ s
345 while one listener with impaired hearing was considered with the normal-hearing standard deviation of 65 μ s . This
346 led to an increase of predicted SRTs in the dichotic condition and on average better agreement with measured SRTs
347 for the hearing-impaired listeners. This indicates that binaural tone-in-noise detection data might be used to adapt the
348 binaural inaccuracy in the EC model in order to improve individual speech intelligibility predictions. This has to be
349 evaluated with more listeners in an experiment where the tone-in-noise BMLD is measured at 500 Hz in order to predict
350 the BMLD for speech. However, the individualized prediction of the BMLD for speech failed for the listeners with
351 normal hearing because the variation observed in the tone detection thresholds was much smaller than the variation
352 in the binaural SRTs. This might be due to the low-pass filtered speech stimuli, which were used to increase the effect
353 size in the SRT measurements, as this might have caused the problem that the normally hearing listeners did not
354 reach optimal performance as they were not used to low-pass filtered speech, even though some training was provided.
355 Given these observations, we, so far, hesitate to recommend using binaural 500 Hz tone-in-noise detection tasks to
356 individualize BSIM's predictions of SRT data. Before such a recommendation might be justified, much more data of
357 listeners with normal and with impaired hearing is required for both tone-in-noise detection and BMLDs for speech.
358 This is far beyond the scope of this study, which had a too extensive measurement scope per listener for a large sample
359 of listeners with hearing impairment. For that reason, we encourage to measure tone-in-noise detection in studies about
360 binaural speech recognition, so that future studies can answer this question.

361 **5. Conclusions**

- 362 • In this study it was shown that the processing inaccuracy in EC processing suggested by vom Hövel [16], which has
363 so far only been evaluated for binaural tone-in-noise detection at 500 Hz, also holds for higher frequencies. This is

364 a consequence of the realization of the errors in the time domain as they implicitly mirror the loss of phase locking
365 in the auditory system with increasing frequency.

- 366 • For lower frequencies (we tested 250 Hz), the processing inaccuracy of the EC stage needs to be increased to
367 approximately 130 μ s in order to account for dichotic tone-in-noise detection thresholds at 250 Hz leading to a
368 bandpass characteristic of the EC processing inaccuracies rather than a low pass characteristic.
- 369 • Broader binaural filters (2.3 ERB) better describe measured BMLDs for large ITDs/IPDs of the noise, indicating
370 that across frequency processing plays a role in binaural unmasking.
- 371 • Furthermore, it was shown for a small ensemble of listeners with hearing impairment that binaural tone-in-noise
372 detection thresholds at 500 Hz can be used to derive estimate an increased binaural processing inaccuracies, which
373 improved the prediction accuracy of the EC-model even for other frequencies and which can help to improve
374 individual binaural speech intelligibility predictions of BSIM.

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380 **Conflicts of interest**

381 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

382 **Data availability statement**

383 The experimental data will be made available on request.

384 **Ethical approval**

385 All participants received hourly compensation and gave informed consent for their participation in the experiments.
386 The methods were approved by the ethics committee of the University of Oldenburg (protocol Drs.-Nr. 04/2018).

387 **References**

- 388 1. Mathieu Lavandier and John F. Culling. Prediction of binaural speech intelligibility against noise in rooms. *The Journal*
389 *of the Acoustical Society of America*, 127(1):387–399, January 2010. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL [http://asa.scitation.org/doi/](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.3268612)
390 [10.1121/1.3268612](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.3268612).

- 391 2. Rainer Beutelmann, Thomas Brand, and Birger Kollmeier. Revision, extension, and evaluation of a binaural speech intel-
 392 ligibility model. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 127(4):2479–2497, April 2010. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL
 393 <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.3295575>.
- 394 3. Rui Wan, Nathaniel I. Durlach, and H. Steven Colburn. Application of an extended equalization-cancellation model to
 395 speech intelligibility with spatially distributed maskers. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 128(6):3678–
 396 3690, December 2010. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.3502458>.
- 397 4. Sam Jelfs, Mathieu Lavandier, and John F. Culling. Revision and validation of a binaural model for speech intelligibility
 398 in noise. *Hearing Research*, page 9, 2011.
- 399 5. Asger Heidemann Andersen, Jan Mark de Haan, Zheng-Hua Tan, and Jesper Jensen. A method for predicting the intel-
 400 ligibility of noisy and non-linearly enhanced binaural speech. In *2016 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics,*
 401 *Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 4995–4999, Shanghai, March 2016. IEEE. ISBN 978-1-4799-9988-0. . URL
 402 <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7472628/>.
- 403 6. Alexandre Chabot-Leclerc, Ewen N. MacDonald, and Torsten Dau. Predicting binaural speech intelligibility using the
 404 signal-to-noise ratio in the envelope power spectrum domain. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 140(1):
 405 192–205, July 2016. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.4954254>.
- 406 7. Christopher F. Hauth and Thomas Brand. Modeling Sluggishness in Binaural Unmasking of Speech for Maskers With
 407 Time-Varying Interaural Phase Differences. *Trends in Hearing*, 22:2331216517753547, 2018. . URL [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.1177/2331216517753547)
 408 [1177/2331216517753547](https://doi.org/10.1177/2331216517753547).
- 409 8. Christopher F. Hauth, Simon C. Berning, Birger Kollmeier, and Thomas Brand. Modeling Binaural Unmasking of Speech
 410 Using a Blind Binaural Processing Stage. *Trends in Hearing*, 24:233121652097563, January 2020. ISSN 2331-2165, 2331-
 411 2165. . URL <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2331216520975630>.
- 412 9. Volker Hohmann. Frequency analysis and synthesis using a gammatone filterbank. *Acta Acustica united with Acustica*, 88
 413 (3):433–442, 2002.
- 414 10. N. I. Durlach. Equalization and Cancellation Theory of Binaural Masking-Level Differences. *The Journal of the Acoustical*
 415 *Society of America*, 35(8):1206–1218, August 1963. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.1918675>.
- 416 11. ANSI S3.5-1997. Methods for Calculation of the Speech Intelligibility Index, 1997.
- 417 12. H. J. M. Steeneken and T. Houtgast. A physical method for measuring speech-transmission quality. *The Journal of the*
 418 *Acoustical Society of America*, 67(1):318–326, January 1980. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL [http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.384464)
 419 [1.384464](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.384464).
- 420 13. Cees H. Taal, Richard C. Hendriks, Richard Heusdens, and Jesper Jensen. An Algorithm for Intelligibility Prediction of
 421 Time-Frequency Weighted Noisy Speech. *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 19(7):2125–2136,
 422 September 2011. ISSN 1558-7916, 1558-7924. . URL <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5713237/>.
- 423 14. Yong Feng and Fei Chen. Nonintrusive objective measurement of speech intelligibility: A review of methodology. *Biomedical*
 424 *Signal Processing and Control*, 71:103204, January 2022. ISSN 17468094. . URL [https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/](https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1746809421008016)
 425 [pii/S1746809421008016](https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1746809421008016).
- 426 15. Rainer Beutelmann and Thomas Brand. Prediction of speech intelligibility in spatial noise and reverberation for normal-
 427 hearing and hearing-impaired listeners. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 120(1):331–342, July 2006. ISSN
 428 0001-4966. . URL <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.2202888>.
- 429 16. Harald vom Hövel. *Zur Bedeutung der Übertragungseigenschaften des Aussenohrs sowie des Binauralen Hörsystems bei*
 430 *Gestörter Sprachübertragung (On the importance of the transmission properties of the outer ear and the binaural auditory*

- 431 *system in disturbed speech transmission*). Ph.D. Dissertation, RWTH Aachen, 1984.
- 432 17. Ted L Langford and Lloyd A Jeffress. Effect of Noise Crosscorrelation on Binaural Signal Detection. *The Journal of the*
433 *Acoustical Society of America*, 36(8):1455–1458, August 1964. .
- 434 18. James P. Egan. Masking-Level Differences as a Function of Interaural Disparities in Intensity of Signal and of Noise. *The*
435 *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 36(10):1992–1992, October 1964. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL [http://asa.scitation.](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.1939216)
436 [org/doi/10.1121/1.1939216](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.1939216).
- 437 19. Steven van de Par and Armin Kohlrausch. Dependence of binaural masking level differences on center frequency, masker
438 bandwidth, and interaural parameters. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 106(4):1940–1947, October 1999.
439 ISSN 0001-4966. . URL <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.427942>.
- 440 20. Leslie R. Bernstein and Constantine Trahiotis. The normalized correlation: Accounting for binaural detection across center
441 frequency. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 100(6):3774–3784, December 1996. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL
442 <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.417237>.
- 443 21. P. M. Zurek and N. I. Durlach. Masker-bandwidth dependence in homophasic and antiphase tone detection. *The Journal*
444 *of the Acoustical Society of America*, 81(2):459–464, February 1987. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL [http://asa.scitation.org/doi/](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.394911)
445 [10.1121/1.394911](http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.394911).
- 446 22. David Mcalpine, Sarah Thompson, Katharina Von Kriegstein, Torsten Marquardt, Timothy Griffiths, and Adenike Deane-
447 Pratt. A π -Limit for Coding ITDs: Neural Responses and the Binaural Display. In Birger Kollmeier, Georg Klump, Volker
448 Hohmann, Ulrike Langemann, Manfred Mauermann, Stefan Uppenkamp, and Jesko Verhey, editors, *Hearing – From Sensory*
449 *Processing to Perception*, pages 399–406, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2007. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. ISBN 978-3-540-73009-5.
- 450 23. Laurel H. Carney. Supra-Threshold Hearing and Fluctuation Profiles: Implications for Sensorineural and Hidden Hearing
451 Loss. *Journal of the Association for Research in Otolaryngology*, 19(4):331–352, August 2018. ISSN 1525-3961, 1438-7573.
452 . URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10162-018-0669-5>.
- 453 24. David Hülsmeyer and Birger Kollmeier. How much individualization is required to predict the individual effect of suprathresh-
454 old processing deficits? assessing plomp’s distortion component with psychoacoustic detection thresholds and fade. *Hearing*
455 *Research*, 426:108609, 2022. ISSN 0378-5955. . URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378595522001770>.
- 456 25. Tobias Neher, Kirsten C. Wagener, and Matthias Latzel. Speech reception with different bilateral directional process-
457 ing schemes: Influence of binaural hearing, audiometric asymmetry, and acoustic scenario. *Hearing Research*, 353:36–48,
458 September 2017. ISSN 03785955. . URL <http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0378595517301193>.
- 459 26. Kirsten Carola Wagener, Volker Kühnel, and Birger Kollmeier. Entwicklung und Evaluation eines Satztests für die deutsche
460 Sprache I: Design des Oldenburger Satztests [development and evaluation of a sentence test for the german language i: Design
461 of the oldenburg sentence test]. *Zeitschrift für Audiologie*, 38(1):4–15, 1999.
- 462 27. Kirsten Carola Wagener, Thomas Brand, and Birger Kollmeier. Entwicklung und Evaluation eines Satztests für die deutsche
463 Sprache Teil II: Optimierung des Oldenburger Satztests [development and evaluation of a sentence test for the german
464 language ii: Optimization of the oldenburg sentence test]. *Zeitschrift für Audiologie*, 38(2):44–56, 1999.
- 465 28. Kirsten Carola Wagener, Thomas Brand, and Birger Kollmeier. Entwicklung und Evaluation eines Satztests für die deutsche
466 Sprache Teil III : Evaluation des Oldenburger Satztests [development and evaluation of a sentence test for the german
467 language iii: Evaluation of the oldenburg sentence test]. *Zeitschrift für Audiologie*, 38(3):86–95, 1999.
- 468 29. Thomas Brand and Birger Kollmeier. Efficient adaptive procedures for threshold and concurrent slope estimates for psy-
469 chophysics and speech intelligibility tests. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 111(6):2801–2810, June 2002.
470 ISSN 0001-4966. . URL <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.1479152>.

- 471 30. Brian C. J. Moore and Brian R. Glasberg. Suggested formulae for calculating auditory-filter bandwidths and excitation
472 patterns. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 74(3):750–753, September 1983. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL
473 <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.389861>.
- 474 31. International Organization for Standardization. Acoustics — reference zero for the calibration of audiometric equipment
475 — part 7: Reference threshold of hearing under free-field and diffuse-field listening conditions. ISO 389-7:2019, 2019. EN
476 ISO 389-7:2019, Edition 3.
- 477 32. Rainer Beutelmann, Thomas Brand, and Birger Kollmeier. Prediction of binaural speech intelligibility with frequency-
478 dependent interaural phase differences. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 126(3):1359–1368, September
479 2009. ISSN 0001-4966. . URL <http://asa.scitation.org/doi/10.1121/1.3177266>.